

Alisher Navoi is a great poet

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Abstract: The article tells the story Alisher Navoi of life and work, and the difficulties he faced in life. Events about his life, His historical works, translation activities and activities as a poet, his role and place in Uzbek literature are described.

Keywords and expressions: Alisher Navoi, poet, epics, "Hamsa", devans, madrasa, rabat, mosque, devans, "mukarrabi hazrati sultan", "Sittai Zaruriya", "Fusuli Arbaa", "Khalati Pahlawon Muhammad".

Alisher Navoi (1441-1501) is a great poet and thinker, statesman. His full name is Nizamiddin Mir Alisher Navoi. Under the pseudonym Navoi, he wrote in Chigatai (both Uzbek language) and Farsi (his works in Persian language). In the West, Chigatai literature is considered the largest manifestation of Uzbek literature.

Navoi was a friend of the future ruler of Khurasan (Transoxania) Husayn Boykara (1469-1506) from his youth. He started writing poems at the age of 10-12. According to the information left by the historian Khondamir (1473(76)-1534), a contemporary of Navoi, the famous Uzbek poet Lutfiy (1369-1465) met the boy Navoi in his old age and noticed his poetic talent.

During his life, Navoi visited different countries of the Muslim East and met famous people of his time. Improves his poetic skills. 1464-1465 Shinavandas of Navoi's work prepare his first poetry collection (devans). It can be seen that Navoi was already a famous poet in those days. Until 1469, Navoi was forced to live far from his hometown Herat due to internal conflicts between the Timurids.

In 1469, Timurid Husayn Boykara captured Herat and became the ruler of Khurasan. From this time on, a new stage of Navoi's life begins. He takes an active part in the political life of the country. In the same year, the ruler of Khurasan appointed Navoi as the state seal, and in 1472 he became a minister. Through his position, he provides great support in the cultural and scientific development of the country.

In 1480, several madrasas, 40 rabats (stations for passengers), 17 mosques, 10 Sufi residences (khanaqahs), 9 baths, 9 bridges and builds others. However, the palace officials do not like Navoi's activities and through various conspiracies they destroy relations with Husayn Boykara.

Thus, Navoi was released from his position and sent to Astrobad as a ruler in 1487. He will serve here for two years. Only after the end of this period, Kh. Boykara allows him to return to Herat and have a position in the government. But Navoi rejects this offer. Despite his refusal, Boykara offers him the position of the sultan's close friend ("mukarrabi hazrati sultan"). In this position, Navoi had the right to make decisions in all matters related to state affairs.

From this time, a new stage of Navoi's life begins and he is more creative. Most of his works belong to this period. Navoi lived and created during the last years of Timurid rule (1370-1506). Therefore, public spirit and important problems specific to the era prevail in his works. 1490-1501 Navoi created his most elegant, socio-philosophical and scientific works. In the years 1483-1485, Navoi created the work "Hamsa", which included five epics: "Hayrat ul-Abror" ("The Admiration of Good People"), "Farhad and Shirin", "Layli and Majnun", "Sabai Sayyor" ("Seven Planets"), "Saddi Iskandari" ("Iskander's Wall").

Navoi tries his pen in almost all genres of the Muslim East and can show that he has his own voice and style. In Eastern literature, more than 120 epics have been created on the theme of "Layli and Majnun". Navoi also writes an epic on this topic with his personal approach. The story tells about the love between Layli and Majnun. Navoi also expressed his Sufi views in the epics "Farkhod va Shirin" and "Hayrat ul-Abror". In his epics, the topic of Sufism is raised to a general philosophical level.

In these epics, at the same time, the current problems of the world are presented through the humanitarian world views of the poet. In two other epics of "Hamsa" – "Sabai Sayyor as it turned out, Navoi was close to the Timurid palace and was able to influence his friend and king Husayn Boygaro. In the fund of the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni alone, there are 166 manuscripts recopied in the 15th-20th centuries, which make up the complete work "Hamsa" or its separate epics. 84 of them are in the form of complete epics. The quantity and wide distribution of Navoi's "Hamsa" show that he occupied a special place in the intellectual life of Central Asia.

Alisher Navoi combined literary works with politics throughout his life. Being a person with a high position, he made a great contribution to the socio-economic improvement of the country's life; patronized the development of science, art, and always tried to ensure that peace and harmony always prevailed. Navoi collected his poems written in Persian under the name Devoni Foni". He also wanted to compete with Persian poets. If we count the ghazals released in the form of a collection, they amount to 3150 pieces. It is no exaggeration to say that Navoi is the leader in terms of the number of poems he wrote. Also, Navoi collected his odes in Persian language and created two collections called "Sittai Zaruriya" ("Six Necessities") and "Fusuli Arbaa" ("Four Seasons of the Year").

In addition, he created treatises on historical topics: "Tarihi muluki Adjam" ("History of the Kings of Iran"), "Tarihi anbiya wa hukama" ("History of Prophets and Sages"). He collected his artistic letters in the collection "Munshaat". His royal works include: About the life of Abd Ar-Rahman Jami – "Khamsat al-mutahayirin", 1494, "Khalati Sayyid Hasan Ardasher" ("The life of Sayyid Hasan Ardasher"), "Khalati Pahlawon Muhammad" ("The life of Pahlawon Muhammad"). Alisher Navoi's last work is "Mahbub ul-Qulub" (1500). It describes the poet's latest social and political views.

Alisher Navoi combined literary works with politics throughout his life. Being a person with a high position, he made a great contribution to the socio-economic improvement of the country's life; sponsored the development of science, art, and science; He always tried to make peace and harmony prevail. As we can see, Navoi's legacy is diverse in terms of themes and genres. His works have served for the development of Uzbek literature from the 15th century to the present day.

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